

Promoting National Integration In Nigeria Through Indigenous Languages: Illustrations From The Igbo Language

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Abstract

The multifarious makeup of Nigeria in addition to the awkward manner of the country's creation poses a problem to the unity of the nation. There is the challenge of unifying all the forces in the country so as to give the idea of one nation. National integration is the ultimate goal to be achieved in a multi-ethnic country like Nigeria for there to be any reasonable development. It is very crucial in the building of a vigorous and comfortable nation. National integration is the awareness of a common identity among the citizens of a country. It is the sense of concord that comes from a background of unified and peaceful co-existence of the distinct ethnic nationalities and culture. Agreed, that Nigeria is a multi-cultural society with a basket of different religions and world-views, this paper argues that it is possible to achieve laudable integration in the country. The paper collected data from documented materials. The analysis of data indicates that unfairness based on the social class, religion, language and culture is the archenemy of national integration in Nigeria. The paper proposes the use of indigenous languages (Igbo) in promoting national integration. A spirited effort by well-meaning individuals and government is suggested in cultivating a sense of oneness needed for national integration.

Key words: National integration, Language, Indigenous languages.

1. Introduction

National Integration has long been seen as an important focus for post-colonial African government. Following the declaration that the “motto of the Federal Republic of Nigeria shall be Unity and Faith, Peace and Progress”, the 1999 constitution pledged that national integration shall be strongly encouraged while

prejudice on the grounds of place of origin, sex, religion, status, ethnic or linguistic association or ties shall be prohibited. National Integration is the key to the realisation of unity and faith, peace and progress (Gbadegesin 2014).

The expression “national integration” consists of two words – ‘national’ and ‘integration’. The word national is the adjective of the noun

nation. The definition of nation can be approached from three perspectives; cultural, psychological and political.

Wellman (2003) captures these three perspectives in his definition of a nation -“A nation is a cultural group of people who identify with one another and either have or seek some degree of political self-determination”. The cultural aspect of a nation demands the common possession of certain cultural elements like language, dressing, values, etiquette, traditions, crafts, mores, history etc. The psychological aspect emphasizes the consciousness of these possessions and the collective identity which they foist on all possessors. On the other hand, it is the political aspect that calls for self-determination. The word integration means the fusion of the people into one. National integration means national unity; that is unity in diversity. It refers to unifying all the forces in a country so as to give the idea of “One Nation”. It also entails social, political, economic, linguistic and cultural unity. National integration is also known as nationalism. It is the ultimate goal to be achieved in a multi-ethnic country like Nigeria for there to be any reasonable development. Nigeria adopted federalism as a means of achieving its much-needed goal of national integration. In essence, the federalism so adopted is expected to reduce the immensely aggressive inter-ethnic competition and tension, allaying the usually alleged fear of domination, bringing government nearer to the people and give the

different groups more opportunities, thereby integrating the country (Chime 1971).

National Integration is a positive notion that promotes the growth and advancement of a particular nation. It builds up national unity and harmony, which is not enforced by any authority. National integration can be attained only with the unified effort of all individuals with the collaborative efforts of the government to fix the obstacles to national unity thereby securing the national interests.

Language plays a vital role in any human community. The language of any human society tells a lot about that society and therefore can be further emphasized that language and any society are intertwined. The functions of language in any human community include the following: expression of thought, political administration, education, social, religious, legislation and so on. The communication of national development is made possible only with the instrumentality of language. Language is used to advance to the citizens the best possible reasons in support of government developmental objectives, projecting in the best possible manner the advantages expected to be drawn from the national development objectives.

An indigenous language is a language that is native to a region and spoken by indigenous people. It is the language spoken uniquely by an indigenous community or country. It is a

language from a linguistically distinct community that has been settled in the area for many generations. Government's programmes and policies reach the grassroots with the use of indigenous languages.

This paper emphasizes that despite the multicultural nature of Nigeria, national integration is achievable through the use of indigenous languages. The work will be handled under the following sub-headings- Introduction, Views on national integration; National integration and language; Indigenous languages and National integration; Examples from other multi-cultural nations; Promoting national integration through indigenous (Igbo) language. The work concludes with suggestions on practical ways to promote national integration.

2. Views on National Integration

National integration is the recognition of a common identity among the citizens of a country. It means that though we belong to different castes, religions and regions and speak different languages, we recognize the fact that we are all one. This understanding is very crucial in the building of a strong and wealthy nation.

Jacob and Tenue (1964:9) as cited in Edosa (2014) define national integration as "a relationship of community among people within the same political entity... a state of mind

or disposition to be cohesive; to act together; to be committed to mutual programmes".

In their contribution, Coleman and Rosberg (1964:9) view national integration as the progressive reduction of cultural and regional tensions and discontinuities in the process of creating a homogenous political community. Also, Deutsch et al (1966:2) defines national integration as "the attainment within a territory of a 'sense of community' and of institutions and practices strong enough and wide-spread enough to assure, for a long time, dependable expectations of peaceful community".

The above views on national integration point to the fact that national integration is a kind of awareness inculcated in the hearts of citizens of a particular country about their common identity. The awareness of oneness in turn affects the overall relationships among the citizens.

According to Chime (1971:50) national integration is "a process of cohesion between two or more social units whereby these units come together to constitute a political whole which include among others the joining of various parts of society into a functioning whole, the growth of obedience and loyalty to its parts and the emergence of shared national values".

Eisinger (1976:53) first, looks at national integration as a situation in which diverse groups in a political system have been successful in developing common institutions

and norms by which to settle conflicts peacefully or pursue collective goals cooperatively, depending on the situation. Going a step further, he describes national integration as a psychological and educational process involving the development of a feeling of unity, solidarity and cohesion in the hearts of the people, a sense of economic citizenship; a feeling of loyalty to the nation”.

Samuel (2015) observes that the following ideas come to mind whenever we talk of national integration or nationalism:

1. A feeling of brotherhood in the midst of the people
2. A feeling of oneness
3. A feeling of cohesion
4. A feeling of harmony in thought and action
5. A feeling of loyalty to the country
6. A feeling of solidarity
7. A feeling of patriotism
8. A feeling of unity of the country
9. A feeling of tolerance with others ideas and beliefs
10. A feeling of ‘WE’ and ‘I’

Agreeing with the above perception, Radharishnan (2010) opines that “national integration cannot be built by brick and mortar; it cannot be built by chisels and hammer. It has to grow silently in the minds and hearts of men. He suggests that the only process to achieve a lasting national integration in a nation like Nigeria is the process of education.

Commenting on the foregoing, Nikky (2010) emphasizes that national integration has to start in the minds of the citizens of a country; it has to be cultivated, sown and watered in the consciousness of the individuals in a nation.

Shona (2003) in Okorie and Greg (2013) says national integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country. In his words, Edosa (2014) sees national integration as a situation where the members of a state see themselves as one; treat one another fairly and work together cooperatively and freely give to and resolve the differences peacefully in the overall interest of the nation.

Contributing to the meaning of national integration, Miah (2016) says it is “that awareness of a typical identity amongst the voters of a rustic”. It follows that although citizens belong to totally different castes, religions and regions and have totally different linguistic backgrounds, they have an understanding of the actual fact that they are all one. This implies the feeling of togetherness towards ones’ own country irrespective of their individual differences with regard to religion, race, culture or caste. Singh (2017) says national integration is not only about national spirit. It involves a feeling that brings people from all areas, dialects and beliefs together in a common endeavour. When national integration occurs, individuals are likely to work together to build systems that enhance the prosperity of a nation and its people. Some things that can get

in the way of national integration include religious or political divides as well as communication barriers between citizens. This supports the argument of Samuel (2015) above; national integration is more of what happens in the minds of the citizen of a nation than the outward manifestations or evidences of the integration. Roy (2017) is also of the same opinion when he describes national integration as the togetherness and oneness felt by the citizens (even after having differences in caste, creed, religion, culture, languages, region, etc) of any country to maintain the national unity and integrity as well as build a strong and prosperous nation. If the citizen have no inbuilt understanding of oneness irrespective of the differences, all other attempts at enforcing national integration will amount to efforts in futility.

Mulu (2017) sees national integration as “the act of bringing together various communities using ways that make them one nation irrespective of their diverse cultures and background”.

It is a useful concept to instil the feelings of oneness among varied areas of society. It is not the sameness of all religions, dress and food habits etc. It means conservation of different cultures and at the same time living; respecting and working in harmony with each other for the overall prosperity of the nation.

3. The Need for National Integration

Nigeria is essentially a plural society; its components groups are separated apart from each other by significant differences of language, ethnicity and cultures. Nigeria is a country with about 250 ethnic nationalities distinctively isolated in terms of religion and languages (Cornelius 2013).

The crises of national integration in Nigeria are very severing such that the Nigerian federation is at its collapsing point. The heterogeneous nature of the country combined with the improper mode of the country’s formation gave rise to antagonistic and integrative processes (Political science project). Nigeria is a country of different caste, races, religions, politics, language, cultures, faiths, customs and traditions; and as a result the integrity of this nation is in danger. National integration as Samuel (2015) captures it is needed to:

- Develop national character
- Bring unity in diversity
- Protect from foreign aggression
- To hold democracy
- To face present challenges
- To control narrow tendencies
- To develop Nigerian culture
- For economic progress
- Establishing world peace
- Achieve scientific and technical progress
- Achieve social progress
- Create internal peace

The above reasons for national integration point to the fact that not much could be achieved in a multicultural society like Nigeria until the issue of national integration is rightly placed.

In line with the foregoing, Mulu (2017) highlighted the following importance of national integration:

1. It promotes development of national unity
2. Citizens develop a spirit of responsiveness when dealing with national calamities and disasters.
3. Promotes patriotism and loyalty among the citizens
4. Reduces fear, suspicion and strife.
5. National integration enables a country to develop a sense of national direction hence people develop and work towards achievement of unified (common) national goals.
6. It promotes peaceful co-existence of different ethnic groups and races which in turn enhances rapid development in commerce and industry leading to a social and economic progress of the nation.

Stressing on the importance of national integration, (Nikky 2017) identifies some of the obstacles to national integration to include: communalism, provincialism, unemployment, lack of social sense, casteism, different political parties, lack of good leadership, frustrated youths, domicile restrictions, lack of national character. Going further, Nikky points at some

forces that promote national integration to include: constitution, democracy, national festivals, interdependence, national symbols, communication system and mass media etc.. These forces go a long way to promote national integration in multicultural societies.

In addition to Mulu's view above on the importance of national integration, NCC (2017) outlines the following reasons for the importance of national integration:

- a) Maintenance of sovereignty and territorial integrity of the nation.
- b) Maintenance of peace and harmony
- c) Growth and development of the nation
- d) Eradication of poverty and illiteracy
- e) Internal security and law and order.
- f) Culture and religious development
- g) Economic and industrial growth
- h) Attraction of foreign investment and increases import and export
- i) Exchange of technological know-how and cultural
- j) Dignity and self respect as a nation
- k) Welfare and well-being of the people
- l) Foreign relations and better standing among the nations of the world.

The importance of national integration as shown above reveals that national integration is a prerequisite for any nation to move forward.

Over the years, different programmes aimed at promoting national integration in Nigeria have

been employed by different governments at various times. Some of them are:

- Introduction of federalism in Nigeria
- Creation of states and the land use decree
- The national Youth Service Corps created by Decree No.24 of May 22, 1973
- The federal Character Principle; a policy aimed at achieving the fair and effective representation of the various components of the federation in the country's position of power, status and influence (Ugoh & Ukpere, 2012).
- The movement of the federal capital Territory from Lagos to Abuja
- The introduction of the revenue sharing formula which is aimed at addressing the violence taking place in the oil rich Delta.
- The unifying National policy on Tertiary Education
- The introduction of the principle of National Integration by 1979 constitution, which was a deliberate effort to tackle the problem facing the practice of a true federalism.
- Establishment of unity schools run by the federal government tends to promote unity in diversity
- Introduction of a uniform local Government system in Nigeria.

Edosa (2014) observes that the above measures employed by successive Nigerian governments to unite and preserve and generally keep the country afloat cannot be said to have been really effective as the polity is daily faced with

increasingly monumental crises of insecurity, sectarian violence, ethnic strife, political instability and threats of disintegration.

4. National Integration and Language

Language is a very important and indispensable tool available to man for the facilitation of his day to day activities. The New International Webster's comprehensive Dictionary of the English language (Encyclopaedic edition) defines language as the expression and communication of emotions or ideas between human beings by means of speech and hearing, the sound spoken or heard being systematized and confirmed by usage among a given people over a given period of time. From the above view, language is supposed to communicate the inner intention and reveal what a particular speaker has in mind.

Stork and Widowson (1974) affirm that all languages are highly developed and sophisticated communication systems, all capable of meeting the demands of the society in which they are used and the personal needs of the individual of the society in terms of expressing emotions and giving and receiving information. It is obvious from the above that language and society are inseparable. Rules and norms of the society are passed on to the younger generation by the old generation through the use of language. Through language, man is able to trace the history and way of life of his people from the distant past. Through language, people get to know why their culture

is different from other people's culture. By so doing, they would have respect and regard for the culture of others.

Talking about language, Obafemi (2012) observes that the,

Communication of national development is made possible only with the instrumentality of language. We communicate to our citizens the objectives we want to achieve in our national development. We use language to advance to them the best possible reasons in support of these objectives, projecting in the best possible manner the advantages which we expect to draw from the national development objectives. Also, we detail for them how the outlined goals should be achieved. Also, when progress is made with reference to the national development objectives, it is also communicated to the citizens. All these are majorly done by language. Also, the process of criticising and assessment of national development are done with the instrumentality of language.

The above assertion shows that language is indispensable for any meaningful governmental activities to take place. Any government that belittles the effect of language will not be able to make any headway in governance. Olaoye (2013) affirms that unity means strength or power and it is language that empowers and

unifies people. Summarily, he says "Language therefore confers power on a nation". Adeniran (2017) adds that language which can be used as an effective instrument for national development and the promotion of national consciousness and unity can also be used as a weapon for marginalization and or exclusion in multilingual societies like Nigeria. Unity means strength or power and it is language that unifies people; language therefore accords power on a nation. This is to say that language is a multidimensional tool which when properly utilised can foster national integration.

5. Indigenous Languages and National Integration

Indigenous languages are inherent interface to the people's existence and philosophy of life in general. Ake (2003) holds that the quest to imitate other cultures is a consequence of lack of self-confidence. He finds concrete expression of this on the decision of some African governments to disallow the speaking of African languages and the wearing of African traditional clothes in parliaments. He makes clear that:

The states of mind that produce such behaviour and attitudes cannot be conducive to development. Development requires changes on a revolutionary scale; it is in every sense a heroic enterprise calling for consummate confidence. It is not for people who do not know who

they are and where they are coming from, for such people are unlikely to know where they are going.

According to Nwadike (2004), indigenous language “is the key to the heart of the people. If we lose the key, we lose the people. If we treasure the key and keep it safe, it will unlock the door of wealth or affluence, thus bringing about national development”. Solanke (2006) upholds Nwadike’s conviction repeating that “indigenous languages are treasures of culture and self-identity”.

The National Institute for Cultural Orientation –News (2014) reveals that “The survival of our indigenous languages required our collective efforts and strong will as well as the supportive policies of government especially in the field of education”.

Conveying his view, Obafemi (2012) remarks that Nigeria is often presented as a diverse nation and the diversity is manifest in the number of ethnic group, religions, language and so on that exist in the country. Based on this diversity, some people arrived on the conclusion that Nigeria cannot survive as a united country. Positions like the above raises dust within the Nigerian polity. Obafemi emphasizes that a close looks at the Nigerian languages reveal that they can be source of unity for the country. The language family tree shows that most Nigerian languages belong in the same Niger-Congo language family. For instance, such languages like Fulani, Igbo, Edo,

and Yoruba etc. belong to the same Niger-Congo family of language. This points to cultural and blood affinity between these groups.

This reveals that indigenous languages can be utilised in fostering a united Nigerian. When Nigeria is united, when all of its parts see themselves as the same because they take into account their relatedness; it will give room for cooperation. This cooperation will in no small measure make the country strong and self-reliant.

Olaoye (2013) opines that individuals develop educationally, socially, economically, politically and culturally through their interaction with government agencies that disseminate ideas and policies through various media in the languages that the individuals’ best understand. This brings to light the fact that people responds better to information when it is circulated in a familiar language.

Airing his view, Adeniran (2017) declares: “If concrete national development must take place within the context and essence of grass-root mobilisation and participation, then the question of utilizing the language of the people, the indigenous languages without resorting to ethnic nationalism, cannot be side-stepped”. It is a requisite cultural heritage with which all forms of human interaction are carried out.

6. Examples from Other Multi-cultural Countries

Multicultural countries are countries with various ethnic groups. It is a situation where multiple cultural traditions exist.

India is a very large country, with the second largest population in the world. About one thousand, six hundred and fifty-two languages and dialects are spoken in the country. From among these, eighteen have been given special recognition by the constitution as official languages of the country at the state level. A unique feature of India is that all the major religions of the world are practised in the country; like Hinduism, Islam, Christianity, Buddhism, Sikhism, Jainism, and Zoroastrianism etc. There are also varieties in costume, food habits and social custom. Despite all these differences, India is a political entity, every part of which is governed under the same constitution. The citizens co-exist with each other peacefully; respect the culture and religion of their fellow Indians (Wanogho 2011).

Another country with multiplicity of culture is America. As Wanogho (2011) also depicts,

America is a country that shares such complexities as Nigeria. But in spite of their differences, Martin Luther King Jr. was able to bring his dream to fruition, given his congenital ability and thorough understanding of the struggle, and what it

would take to grapple with the forces of segregation, oppression and suppression.

Martin Luther consciously and deliberately deemphasized racism, ethnicity, religion, and cultural affiliation, and all the potential bottlenecks, in a bid to achieving the justice they so greatly long for. He preached love with much emphasis on the need to grapple with the undesirable elements in the society. He made it an all inclusive struggle, without regards to race, ethnic divide, cultural and religious affiliation. He consistently preached to the people without boundaries of any sort, creating awareness, regenerating in the people the consciousness of the need to come together in a common front for their emancipation. All this he did with one conviction, bearing in mind that the masses are themselves the last hope for their freedom. Consequently, upon the continuous lectures, seminars, workshops, rallies, and all other effective means of enlightenment campaigns, the masses were galvanized to act and they had no other opinion than to reach a consensus agreement to move for change.

The above examples reveal that Nigeria is not the only country with multiple culture and ethnicity. India and America devised ways to integrate their nations using their indigenous languages; by the Indian constitution, states are free to choose their own official languages. As

a result, there are twenty-two (22) other official languages at the state level (Viswanathan (2012). This is a laudable integration process which gives room for the development of Indian indigenous languages while English remains one of the official languages at the national level. In the case of America, Martin Luther made use of seminars, workshops and enlightenment campaigns to win the people's heart. The seminars, workshops and the enlightenment campaigns, in our opinion are done in a language that is not strange to the people.

7. Promoting National Integration through Igbo Language

National integration is a powerful feeling of 'oneness' which should be sown like seeds in the hearts and minds of people to sprout and grow into 'one nation', one people' as branchless trees (Karan 2017). This is to say that, though we are stratified by caste, creed, religion, region, language, politics and other socio-economic aspects, we have to unite and bind ourselves together by a powerful feeling of "We are one-Nigeria and live for Nigeria-Our nation. Here, we will look at two ways of promoting national integration using indigenous Igbo language.

Every indigenous language especially the developed ones have the standard variety which is studied in institutions of learning. The standard variety is made up of different words from the different dialects that make up the

language. For example, Igbo language is one of the indigenous languages spoken in Nigeria. It is made up of over 20 dialects (Ikekeonwu 1987). These dialects are spoken in different areas of Igbo land. The Igbo language studied in schools is the standard variety (Igbo izugbe) which is a combination of words from the different dialects of Igbo. Some of the dialects are similar and related while some are totally different but they are all versions of the Igbo language. For Igbo people from different parts to have mutual communication, a standard version of the Igbo language was needed. It was this need for integration across Igbo land that led to creating the Igbo language version referred to as the standard Igbo. The language scholars that came up with the standard variety worked tirelessly, though not without some difficulties. The rewarding effect is that today, Igbo people from different linguistic backgrounds can now have a round-table discussion with ease. This is not a day's job; it took some years of intensive and spirited commitment to come by. As at today, much has been accomplished, but it is still an ongoing task that will continue as long as man uses language. To create the standard variety, words were gathered from the different dialects that make up the Igbo language. It was done in a manner that no part of the Igbo land will claim that the standard variety is entirely from their dialect. The standard Igbo is like a reservoir being fed from the different dialects of the Igbo language. The indigenous languages in Nigeria

could be utilized in the same way. Linguists from across the nation should be engaged to start working towards a national language to be built from the numerous indigenous languages in Nigeria.

The second way of promoting national integration in Nigeria, is to inspire a sense of love and devotion in the hearts of the Nigerian citizens towards the country. For the nation to be properly integrated there has to be full-hearted devotion to the nation, sense of duty together with obligation and unquestioning faith in its glorious future based on its present well being and prosperity. Reena (2017) captures national integration as a psychological and emotional process including the development of a feeling of unity, solidarity and cohesion in citizenship and a feeling of loyalty to the nation. This includes social, political, economic, linguistic and cultural unity. The process of integration has to start in the hearts of the citizens and for this to be actualised; language has to come into play. To convince the citizenry of the need for integration as Martin Luther did in America, their emotions must be aroused using a language that is very familiar; and in this case, it is only the indigenous languages that are capable of doing the job. This paper sees Igbo language as capable of being used to promote national integration in Nigeria. The Igbo people are curious and very enterprising; therefore, to get them to appreciate the importance of national integration, the rich

genres of the language could be employed. Some of the rich aspects of the Igbo language that could be used to promote national integration include most of the oral traditional literature like: folktales, proverbs, wellerism, anecdote (parable) etc. Some of these figures of speech could be used to explain the different benefits of national integration. This is because, before an Igbo man ventures into any business, he firstly ascertains what he will gain from it. To get these done, knowledgeable Igbo indigenes with a good grasp of the language should be engaged at the national level; they will be intimated with the need and the benefits of national integration and then commissioned with the task of using Igbo language to teach and convince the Igbo people to see other citizens (non-Igbo) as one irrespective of their cultural background. In the present paper, five proverbs will be analysed to buttress our point.

Some Igbo proverbs that could be used to promote national integration:

1. *Gidi gidi bu ugwu eze* (Pomp and pageantry are the honour of a king)
2. *A nyukoo nwaamiri onu o gbaa ufufu* (Urinating together makes it foamy)
3. *A toro uto tota ihe, see okwu, e seteghi ihe* (we gain living peaceably, but loose in enmity)
4. *Ikwu amaghi, ibe ezi ya* (If one does not know, another will teach him).
5. *Nwanne di na mba* (There is a relation in a distant land).

The first proverb; *Gidi gidi bu ugwu eze* literally means “Pomp and pageantry are the honour of a king” but the actual meaning is that “a king has honour by the numerous people around him”. This implies that what determines the honour a king has is the number of people at his command. This, in relation to Nigeria and national integration is to say that Nigeria is only great because of the numerous ethnicity brought together as one. Without the Igbo people, Nigeria will lose its greatness and Igbo people alone cannot make a great nation. Nigeria needs the Igbo people to remain great while the Igbo people needs Nigeria to be recognised.

Secondly, the second proverb – *A nyukoo nwaamiri onu, o gbaa ufufu* “Urinating together makes it foamy”. This means that “for much to be accomplished there is need for united effort”. This is to say that a lot will be achieved in Nigeria when the different ethnic groups bury their divides and work for a common goal. The interpretation is that the Igbo people will achieve more working together with other tribes in Nigeria than working in isolation.

The third proverb, “*A toro uto tota ihe, see okwu, e seteghi ihe.* “We gain living peaceably, but loose in enmity” actually means that “there is no gain in enmity”. It entails that animosity for each other will only lead to losing a lot; including lives and properties as have been witnessed in Nigeria over the years. On the

contrary, when there is peace and harmony, much will be gained and preserved. The Igbo people will gain nothing by hating other tribes rather; they keep losing a lot (lives and properties).

The fourth proverb, *Ikwu amaghi, ibe ezi ya* “If one does not know, another will teach him”. This means that “we learn from one another”. Nobody has a monopoly of knowledge. We know in parts. There are so many things we can learn from each other if only we humble ourselves. Igbo people can learn from other Nigerian tribes while other tribes can learn from the rich cultures of the Igbo people.

The fifth proverb, *Nwanne di na mba* “There is a relation in a distant land”.

This proverb points to the fact that there can be genuine friends or precious things in a distant land. The Igbo people are travellers and they make good friends wherever they go. Relating this to national integration, it implies that there are wonderful people, precious things and fortune in a distant land; one can only meet or come in contact with wonderful people when one travels around. If Nigeria is integrated; when there is peace and harmony, the Igbo people will keep meeting good people around the nation.

The above proverbs and their interpretations are wonderful tools encapsulated in the indigenous Igbo language which could be of tremendous

use in promoting national integration in Nigeria.

8. Conclusion and Suggestions

The issue of indigenous languages should be handled with total commitment and seriousness. Let us embrace our language with enthusiasm and pride and promote what we have together. The paper suggests that a body of committed linguists be set up in Nigeria. This body will be financed and commissioned to study all documented indigenous languages in Nigeria to come up with a standard indigenous language which will serve as a national language in Nigeria. It should be a long term (if not a lifelong) project since language is will continue to endure as human society remains. This suggestion is borrowed from what happens in dialects of different indigenous languages as explained in 1.7 above.

The paper suggests the following measures for a proper and lasting national integration in Nigeria:

1. The use of indigenous language studies at the different levels of Education. We therefore propose the amendment of the National Policy on Education to extend the use of indigenous language in teaching across all levels of education in Nigeria.
2. Making the standard varieties of indigenous languages official languages at state levels while maintaining English language as the official language at the federal level.

3. Promotion of inter-tribal marriages in Nigeria. This will encourage multilingualism among Nigerian citizens.
4. Promotion of inter-ethnic trade among the different regions of the nation.
5. Use of indigenous languages in cultivating the sense of oneness and togetherness in citizens from cradle to adulthood.
6. Introduction of a national integration day in which indigenous languages will be used as official language of the day.
7. Investing in indigenous languages.
8. Encouraging versatility in Nigerian indigenous language.
9. Documentation of indigenous languages.
10. Translation of the Nigerian constitution into Igbo language and other indigenous languages.
11. All non-indigenes in a particular state should in their own interest learn the standard indigenous language of the state wherein they reside.
12. All official work at state level should be carried out in the standard indigenous language.
13. The government should support the National Institute for Cultural Orientation in their effort to train more Nigerians in indigenous languages.

The paper reiterates that if the illustration from Igbo indigenous language and further suggestions given here are followed and applied in other Nigerian indigenous languages, it will

go a long way in promoting national integration in Nigeria.

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